

EXISTENTIAL-HUMANISTIC APPROACHES TO GROUP WORK

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Abstract. *This study provides information on the development of human worldview, spiritual growth, and assessment of psychological states in a group based on existential-humanistic approaches. Analytical results of psychological research, which are important in improving students' cooperation skills in group work, are discussed. Also, instructions are given on the use of modern methods in the use of trainings that help improve a person's mental state in psychological approaches.*

Keywords: *Existential-humanistic approaches, psychological research, worldview, collaborative skills, spirituality, psychological training.*

GURUH ISHIDA EKZISTENSIAL-GUMANISTIK YONDASHUVLAR

Annotatsiya. *Ushbu tadqiqotda ekzistensial-gumanistik yondashuvlarga asoslangan holda guruhda shaxsning dunyoqarashini oshirish, ma'naviy yuksalishi va psixologik holatlarini baholash haqida ma'lumotlar keltirib o'tilgan. Guruh ishida talabalarning kolloborativ ko'nikmalarini oshirishda muhim ahamiyatga ega bo'lgan psixologik tadqiqotlarning tahliliy natijalari muhokama qilinadi. Shuningdek, psixologik yondashuvlarda shaxsning ruhiy ahvolini yaxshilashga yordam beruvchi treninglardan foydalanishda zamonaviy metodlardan foydalanish bo'yicha ko'rsatmalar berib o'tiladi.*

Kalit so'zlar: *Ekzistensial-gumanistik yondashuvlar, psixologik tadqiqotlar, dunyoqarash, kolloborativ ko'nikmalar, ma'naviyat, psixologik treninglar.*

Introduction

The existential-humanistic approach is interpreted as a complex psychological concept focused on the inner world of a person, personal experience, life meaning, and the ability of a person to realize himself in group work. The basis of this approach is the philosophical view that a person is the subject of his own existence, and the life path of each person depends on his choice and responsibility. Existential and humanistic psychology directions turn the group process into a unique space for the self-discovery of the individual, since in these approaches, not the problems of a person are the main thing, but his potential for growth, development, and finding his own meaning. In the group process, participants compare their experiences with the experiences of others, understand their emotional experiences, and have the opportunity to deeply analyze themselves through interpersonal communication.

According to the existential approach, each person has a unique, special place in life, and by understanding this place, the individual feels the need to responsibly manage his life. The importance of such an approach in group work is that group members begin to reveal their true feelings in the process of regular communication, and this process increases their level of self-awareness. Sincere communication, open emotional expression, unconditional acceptance and empathetic listening make the group environment a safe, warm and psychologically stable place.

In such an environment, a person has the opportunity to understand his hidden fears, internal conflicts, lack of purpose in life or difficulties in finding meaning. Each person in the group understands how he affects others by seeing how he affects the actions and feelings of others. This process is an important factor in personal growth. In the existential-humanistic approach, the principle of "here and now" is important, because living with the feelings of the present moment, the process of real communication, and the current situation further deepens the process of human understanding. Such an approach ensures that the national idea becomes not only a theoretical, but also a practical educational force. In modern society, the development of the human personality, its striving for spiritual perfection, and ensuring social activity are recognized as one of the most important directions of psychology and pedagogical sciences. The ideas of in-depth study of the personality, understanding its inner world, and finding the meaning of life are especially expressed in existential and humanistic approaches. These areas emphasize the awareness of a person's identity, a sense of responsibility, striving for a goal, and sincere communication with others as the main values. Today, psychological trainings, group classes, and personal development programs help people understand the meaning of their lives, feel their spiritual responsibility, and form social and spiritual stability. Therefore, existential-humanistic approaches serve as an important methodological basis not only in individual therapy, but also in group work. This study analyzes the theoretical foundations of existential-humanistic approaches in group work, their role and significance in the formation of moral responsibility in training.

Group work is a process of communication, exchange of experiences and self-awareness of several individuals within the framework of a purposeful activity. Group training in psychology is carried out in the form of training, discussion, psychodrama, consulting. In a group, a person sees himself through others, understands his feelings and develops interpersonal communication skills. In an existential-humanistic approach, a group is an opportunity for a person to freely express his thoughts, share life experiences, understand internal problems and solve them. In the group process, an individual gains a deeper understanding of their "We", learns to empathize with the experiences of others, and thereby develops a sense of spiritual responsibility. From a pedagogical point of view, teamwork plays an important role in the socialization of the individual, in the formation of collective decision-making, cooperation, compromise and tolerance skills. In group classes, the teacher or instructor is not a supervisor, but a guide, an assistant. This creates a favorable psychological environment for personal growth. Spiritual responsibility is the ability of a person to make the right decisions based on his beliefs, values and conscience, to feel responsible for his actions. This concept is important not only as a religious or moral, but also as a psychological category. In the existential approach, spiritual responsibility is interpreted as a natural consequence of human freedom. According to Frankl, a person is free, but this freedom is not unlimited - it comes with responsibility.

A person makes a choice to find the meaning of his life and is responsible for this choice.

The existential-humanistic approach is a modern psychological concept aimed at understanding the role, purpose and responsibility of a person in life. In group work, these approaches serve to form personal growth, inner harmony and spiritual maturity. In the process of training, a person feels responsible for his life, learns to understand others and is formed as an active, conscious person in society. Therefore, group training organized on the basis of existential-humanistic approaches is one of the effective ways for a person to understand himself, develop spiritual responsibility, and maintain balance in social life.

We believe that it is appropriate to use collaborative teaching methods in creating a new system based on multi-vector approaches in education. We will further increase the effectiveness of education by forming students' worldviews, improving their skills in working together, and consolidating their knowledge through psychological training. Through this study, we examined the most effective method of group and collective learning. We put forward the idea that this increases the ability of students to remember the knowledge they have received, helps them think freely, reason, and make decisions. During this study, we conducted interviews with students through psychological training and listened to the opinions of students. Psychological research in education provides a brief theoretical overview of research on active and collaborative learning.

Definitions of these learning forms are given. The main characteristics of active and collaborative learning forms are listed. The types of learning activities used in collaborative learning are listed: discussion, peer learning, problem solving, collaborative writing, games.

Possible reasons for the effectiveness of collaborative learning are indicated: socio-psychological factors and the ability to provide a high level of cognitive participation. Based on these studies, information is provided on the practical application of research conducted on the basis of modern pedagogical methods and the organization of psychological training aimed at improving students' collaborative skills. Despite the diversity of psychological exercises used in psychological training sessions, teaching techniques of teachers, and methods used by psychologists in organizing pedagogical methods, several main methodological problems can be identified in psychological training methods. Most of them, cooperative learning (i.e., students in a group collaborative learning process) traditionally includes group discussions and situational role-playing negotiations. In addition, researchers - theorists and practicing psychologists who solve methodological problems of psychological training, propose to include psychophysiological self-regulation methods through the training of interpersonal sensitivity, including training aimed at increasing the sensitivity of students' perception in collaborative learning in a collective way.

Educational psychologists are also advised to use meditative methods and motivational (for teaching self-hypnosis) methods in psychological training. In this approach, the role of the group leader is also interpreted differently. He should not be an authoritarian or commanding person, but a sincere, empathetic and psychologically stable person who helps group members understand their inner experiences. The leader controls the group process, but does not force it; he guides, but does not judge; he deepens communication, but does not interfere with the inner experiences of the participants. His main task is to strengthen mutual trust in the group, allow participants to feel free and encourage them to understand their responsibility in their lives.

The harmony of the leader, that is, the harmony of his internal and external state, is one of the powerful factors that motivate group members to sincerity. The group process discusses existential themes such as death, loneliness, free choice, responsibility, and meaninglessness.

Through discussing these themes, participants reexamine their life positions, gain a deeper understanding of themselves, and more clearly define their goals by reflecting on life's limitations.

Existential-humanistic groups create a productive environment for the individual to discover himself, find his potential, feel responsible for his destiny, and strive for the meaning of life.

Conclusion

In conclusion, the group process can be a powerful catalyst for personal growth because it allows a person to see their inner world through the experiences of others. Personal achievement, inner analysis, emotional relief, self-acceptance, and self-esteem are among the natural results of the group experience. The contribution of the existential-humanistic approach to group work is that it accepts a person as a complex being, allowing him to see his mental, social, spiritual, and emotional aspects as a whole. The mutual experience and exchange of ideas of group members softens the inner contradictions of the individual, reveals his spiritual potential, and strengthens his life goals.

REFERENCES

1. Turemuratova, Aziza, Rita Kurbanova, and Barno Saidboyeva. "EDUCATIONAL TRADITIONS IN SHAPING THE WORLDVIEW OF YOUNG PEOPLE IN FOLK PEDAGOGY." *Modern Science and Research* 2.10 (2023): 318-322.
2. Kurbanova, R. J., and B. E. Saidboeva. "MAKTAB VA OILADA ESTETIK TARBIYANI SHAKLLANTIRISH JARAYONIDA O'QUVCHILARNING AKSILOGIK DUNYOQARASHINI RIVOJLANTIRISH." *Inter education & global study* 9 (2024): 114-121.
3. Jarasovna, Kurbanova Rita. "The Role of National Values in Shaping the Aesthetic Worldview of Schoolchildren." *International Journal of Pedagogics* 5.03 (2025): 55-58.
4. Turemuratova, Aziza, Zuxra Palvanova, and Laura Kazakbaeva. "RULES FOR THE TRAINER'S SELF-CONTROL WHEN CONDUCTING PSYCHOLOGICAL TRAINING." *Modern Science and Research* 4.6 (2025): 312-313.
5. Begibaevna, Turemuratova Aziza, Kushbaeva Indira Tursinbaevna, and Dawletmuratova Raxila Genjemuratovna. "THE MAIN ESSENCE OF DEVELOPING STUDENTS' COLLABORATIVE SKILLS BASED ON MULTI-VECTOR PEDAGOGICAL APPROACHES IN MODERN EDUCATION." *CURRENT RESEARCH JOURNAL OF PEDAGOGICS* 5.09 (2024): 43-46.
6. Turemuratova, Aziza, Shaxnoza Aralbaeva, and Asilxan Amangeldieva. "PSIXOLOGIK TRENINGLARNING USLUBIY MUAMMOLARI VA TRENING BOSQICHLARI." *Modern Science and Research* 4.4 (2025): 212-216.
7. Turemuratova, Aziza, Kutlibike Abdurasuliyeva, and Gu'lnur Musayeva. "GENERAL INFORMATION AND PSYCHOLOGICAL ANALYSIS OF FAIRY TALE THERAPY." *Modern Science and Research* 4.4 (2025): 1205-1210.

8. Turemuratova, Aziza, Ziyra Kalilaeva, and Gulayim Xojanova. "IMPROVING THE PROFESSIONAL SKILLS OF A PSYCHOLOGIST-TRAINER AND DEVELOPING A METHODOLOGY FOR PSYCHOLOGICAL TRAINING." *Modern Science and Research* 4.4 (2025): 782-787.
9. Turemuratova, Aziza, Qundiz Ibragimova, and Juldiz Utegenova. "INFORMATION ABOUT THE PROCESSES AND BASIC RULES FOR WORKING WITH PSYCHOTHERAPEUTIC PRODUCTS." *Modern Science and Research* 4.4 (2025): 908-913.
10. Turemuratova, Aziza, Miyrigu'L. Asamatdinova, and Ardak Mnajatdinova. "TRAINING PSYCHOLOGIST-TRAINERS TO IMPROVE THEIR SKILLS AND ORGANIZE PSYCHOLOGICAL TRAININGS." *Modern Science and Research* 4.4 (2025): 273-278.
11. Turemuratova, Aziza, Renat Urazimbetov, and Miyassar Babajanova. "IMPROVING STUDENTS'COLLABORATIVE SKILLS THROUGH PSYCHOLOGICAL TRAINING AND BASIC RULES FOR THE PRACTICE OF PSYCHOLOGICAL TRAINING." *Modern Science and Research* 4.4 (2025): 532-538.